

THOUGHTS ABOUT DIABETES

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Annotations: Diabetes mellitus is a disease caused by insulin deficiency and metabolic disorders in the body. Diabetes has been known for a long time in the history of Eastern folk medicine. Abu Ali ibn Sina pays special attention to this pain. "Water comes out the way it was drunk," he wrote. If the patient drinks a lot of water, it will cause other diseases and the patient will lose a lot of weight. Stopping the treatment, the doctor says: "Give the patient cold fluids, put them in a cooler, drink sour yogurt, give them fruits, drink mint, that is, wet the patient and cool him." This disease is caused by excess heat in the human body. means that it will appear. According to historical medical sources, diabetes can also be hereditary. In diabetes, there is a sharp increase in blood sugar, it is excreted in the urine (it contains sugar), thirst, weight loss, weakness, body itching and other symptoms are observed.

Key words: diabetes, insulin, type 1

Relevance of the topic: According to the current evidence, it is noted that the number of patients suffering from diabetes is increasing worldwide. Today, the prevalence of this disease among the population is 2%, and 5-8% of them are children under 15 years old. Symptoms, classification, treatment and prevention of diabetes can help patients with diabetes from stress and any negative thoughts, as well as lifestyle changes (regular physical activity, smoking cessation, and diabetes patients increasing knowledge of z). There are widespread misconceptions about diabetes among the people, and diabetes is one of the non-infectious (non-communicable) diseases that have been increasing dramatically in the population in recent years. There are many misconceptions about this disease. That is: "**Diabetes is caused by fear**", "**Diabetes is a disease of the rich**". This article discusses these concepts.

Purpose of the topic: The treatment of diabetes mellitus consists of 4 main components: diet, hypoglycemic agents, increasing physical activity, and learning about diabetes mellitus.

Content of the topic: There are two types of diabetes. Type 1 diabetes is an autoimmune disease. In addition, pancreatotropic (prone to live in the pancreas) viral infections (hepatitis, parotitis, rubella, measles, etc.) play an important role in its origin. Type 2 diabetes is mainly caused by lack of activity, chronic consumption of products

rich in easily digestible carbohydrates, animal fat products in large and excessive amounts, and after that, excess accumulated in the body (mainly in the stomach) The formation of adipose tissue is important.

In addition, chronic stress conditions, long-term insomnia, certain diseases, including hypertension, pancreatitis, obesity, thyrotoxicosis, Itsenko-Cushing syndrome, acromegaly and other diseases, as well as certain drugs (nicotinic acid, glucocorticoids, thyroid hormones) plays an important role in the development of diabetes.

Stressful situations (sudden fear or joy) actually lead to the appearance of symptoms of diabetes in people who are predisposed to diabetes and whose carbohydrate metabolism is disturbed to one degree or another.

The importance of physical work for the normal course of carbohydrate metabolism is very high. The body's energy balance is disrupted when inactivity is allowed due to normal or excessive consumption. The energy received by the body is significantly, even several times more than the energy it spends, and the unused part of the energy accumulates in the body in the form of glycogen and fats.

As this process increases, the sensitivity of the body to insulin decreases, and this condition leads to a violation of carbohydrate metabolism. That is, the occurrence of type 2 diabetes depends not on social status, but on inactivity, wrong and disordered eating.

When the blood sugar analysis is high for the first time, it is necessary to donate blood on a diet for reanalysis.

When a diet is prescribed, the amount of sugar in the blood is significantly reduced compared to its previous state, and it is not possible to assess the actual state of carbohydrate metabolism. A patient suspected of having diabetes should eat normally until a definite diagnosis is made.

A patient with diabetes should be treated in an inpatient setting for 6 months.

The patient must strictly follow this regimen every day. Complications of diabetes can be prevented or delayed only if the amount of sugar in the blood is always within the normal range during the day. Otherwise, it is impossible to prevent the complications of diabetes, even if 10 days a month are treated in the hospital for 6 months. It is not indicated in any endocrinology or diabetology literature that 10 days of inpatient treatment is required every 6 months. Prevention of complications of diabetes mellitus requires strict adherence to the regular regimen of treatment of the disease as indicated above, as well as timely medical examination, general blood,

general urine and biochemical analyzes as indicated in the treatment standards. will be carried out and measures will be taken based on their results.

Eating buckwheat mixed with yogurt is a good remedy for diabetes.

Buckwheat is just an ordinary food product. Yogurt too. It's just that they're lower in carbohydrates, so they don't raise blood sugar as much.

Blue apples do not increase blood sugar.

The taste of an apple depends on the amount of organic acids in its content. The amount of sugar depends not on its color, but on its size and degree of maturity.

You can eat pure honey because half of it is fructose, so it is a sugar substitute and does not raise blood sugar.

Honey consists of roughly equal proportions of fructose and glucose. Consumable sugar (sucrose) is also composed of fructose and glucose residues. Honey has the same blood sugar-raising properties as sugar.

Insulin is prescribed in the last stage of the disease.

In type 1 diabetes, the body loses the ability to produce insulin in a short period of time. That is, insulin-producing cells die in a short period of time. In this case, there is no other way to inject insulin into the body from the outside.

In type 2 diabetes, from the moment the disease is first detected (if there are no serious concomitant diseases), tablets that lower the sugar level are prescribed.

If these patients have severe comorbidities (ischemic heart disease, acute cerebrovascular accident, tuberculosis, severe injuries, pneumonia, and other acute conditions), the blood sugar will remain high even when the maximum daily amount of blood-lowering tablets is prescribed. if the amount does not reach the norm, or during surgical procedures, and before and after (for a certain period of time), an insulin drug is prescribed. A hypoglycemic agent is selected based on the patient's condition, not based on the wishes of the patient and his relatives or the doctor.

Sweets cannot be completely excluded from the diet, because glucose is necessary for brain nutrition.

Brain cells do indeed feed on glucose, but there is no point in giving a diabetic patient extra glucose if his blood sugar is already that high.

conclusion, a person who wants to know about diabetes needs to get information from a qualified professional. Moreover, disseminating such unfounded information as above only harms the patients suffering from diabetes.

List of references

1. Balabolkin MI "Endocrinology", Moscow, 2000.
2. Baranov VG "Manual of clinical endocrinology", Leningrad, 1973.
3. Dedov II "Endocrinology", Moscow, 2000.
4. Dedov II, Mel'nichenko GA, Fadeev VV Endocrinology. M.